

INDIGOID VAT DYES OF THE ISATIN SERIES. PART III 3-INDOLE-2'-(4'-METHYL)-THIONAPHTHENEINDIGOS.

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3-Indole-2'-(4'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo and its various substituted products, the substituents being present in the indole group, have been prepared and their dyeing shades on cotton and on wool compared with those of the corresponding 5'- and 6'-methyl compounds. The change in colour due to Me-substitution in 4, 5 and 6 positions of the thionaphthene nucleus of 3-indole-2'-thionaphtheneindigo has been found to be produced in the same way as observed by the author in the acenaphthenequinone and the aldehyde series.

The effect of Me-groups in a molecule of thioindigo in its 4 : 4', 5 : 5' and 6 : 6' position resembles that of the above two series and also isatin series.

In the acenaphthenequinone series, a study of the isomeric methyl-thionaphthene-acenaphthyleneindigos (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 423; 1933, 10, 679; 1936, 13, 94; 1938, 15, 20) and in the aldehyde series, a study of the isomeric bis-(methyl)-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigos and benzylidene-(methyl)-thionaphthenes (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 659; 1937, 14, 709; 1938, 15, 359; Auwers and Arndt, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 541), has shown that the position of Me-group in the thionaphthene nucleus of the compounds of these two series, is of great influence in deepening or lightening the colour of these isomeric thioindigoid dyes. Of the three positions 4, 5 and 6 of the thionaphthene nucleus, when the Me-group is introduced in 5 position, *i.e.*, *meta* to the indigo chromophore CO, the deepening effect becomes prominent and the colour is lightened when the Me-group enters into 4 and 6 positions, *i.e.* *ortho* and *para* respectively to CO group.

In order to elucidate further the above observation, the present investigation was undertaken. It deals with indigoid dyes obtained by condensing 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1928, 99, 1, 759; E. P. 279489, U. S. P. 28037; Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 23) with isatin and its various derivatives and the following new dyestuffs have been obtained: 3-indole-, 3-(5-chloro)-indole-, 3-(5-bromo)-indole-, 3(5 : 7-dibromo)-indole-, 3-(5-bromo-7-nitro)-indole-, 3-(5:7-dinitro)-indole- 2'-(4'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo (*cf.* Guha and Basu-Mallick, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 395; Guha, *ibid.*, 1937, 14, 240).

As a result of the study of the properties of these isomeric methyl dyes of the isatin series and the quantitative measurement of some of them in xylene solution (Table I), it has been found that the change in colour due to the Me-substitution in 4, 5, and 6 positions of the thionaphthene nucleus

of 3-indole-2'-thionaphtheneindigos (Bezdzik and Friedländer, *Monatsh.*, 1908, 29, 376. E. P. 17162-06; E. P. 6490-07, G. P. 277358, etc.) is produced in the same way (*vide* figures 1, 2 and 3) as was observed in the other two series (*loc. cit.*).

A detailed study of the effect of substitution by Me or Cl on the colour and fastness of thioindigos was recently made by I. G. Farben industrie and the Society of Chemical Industry, Basel. The 4:4'-dimethylthioindigo appeared to be particularly fast to light (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1928, 99, I, 759 *et seq*; Thorpe and Linstead, "Synthetic dystuff" 1933, p. 203), but nothing has been mentioned there with regard to the colour and the depth of colour of the alkyl thioindigos.

FIG. 1.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to 3-indole-2', -2'-(6'-methyl-, 5'-methyl- and -4'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigos.

Thioindigo, 4:4',5:5', and its 6:6'-dimethyl derivatives (Friedländer, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 1060; E. P. 279489; U. S. P. 28037; Auwers and Arndt, *loc. cit.*; Friedlander, 9, 589, D. R. P. 204763, Auwers and Thies, *Ber.*, 1920, 53, 2285) were prepared and their absorption spectra taken in xylene solution with a view to study the depth of colour and compare the relationship with the dyestuffs of the acenaphthenequinone, aldehyde and isatin series recently studied by the present author. The absorption curves (Fig. 4) of each of these four substances show two maxima. The wave-length was deduced for both the points of each curve and mentioned in Table II. From the curves and wave-lengths the influence of Me-groups in 4:4'- and 6:6'- position of thioindigo have been found to lighten the colour, the maximum effect being in 6:6'- position; the influence in 5:5'- position is to deepen the colour of the

FIG. 2.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to 3-(5:7-dibromo)-indole-2', -2'(4':5'), and 6'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigos,

parent substance. It may be pointed out here that of the two wavelengths calculated for 6:6'-dimethylthioindigo, the longer one does not indicate the maximum lightening effect (Table II). The effect of Me-groups in a molecule of thioindigo in above positions in general resembles that of the acenaphthenequinone, aldehyde and isatin series (*cf.* Friedlander, *Ber.*, 1916, **49**, 955).

The dyestuffs described in this paper have imparted full shades on cotton from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat, the colour of which is similar to that of the vat obtained from the corresponding 5'- and 6'-methyl derivatives. They dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid giving a blue solution in each case. These compounds, with the exception of the bromonitro and the dinitro derivatives, dye wool from an acid bath giving uniformly and fully developed shades. They also develop lustre when rubbed hard. When

FIG. 3.

Curves 1, 3—4 refer respectively to 3-(5:7-dinitro) indole-2'(4'-methyl-, 5'-methyl-, and 6'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigos.

Curve 2 refers to 3-(5:7-dinitro)-indole-2'-thionaphtheneindigo.

heated above 300°, they melt and quickly volatilise. The 4'-methyl dyes, prepared from isatin and its 5-chloro- and 5-bromo derivative, have developed colours on cotton and on wool which are deeper than those of the nearly corresponding compounds in the acenaphthenequinone series.

The colours of the dyeings on wool and on cotton obtained from the isomeric methyl compounds of this series are given in Table I for comparison. The 4', 5', and 6'-methyl derivatives of 3-(5:7-dinitro)-indole-2'-thionaphtheneindigo were prepared by the present author (Parts I, II and III). The parent compound has now been obtained and the properties investigated. The absorption spectra of this dinitro compound, 3-indole-2'-thionaphtheneindigo (Thioindigo scarlet R) and its dibromo derivative (Ciba Red G) were taken, the curves drawn (Figs. 1, 2 and 3) and also their wave lengths deduced for comparison with their isomeric methyl derivatives (Table I).

FIG. 4.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to 6:6', 5:5', 4:4'-dimethylthioindigos⁺ and thioindigo.

TABLE I.

T = Thionaphtheneindigo.

Compounds.	Colour in concen- trated H ₂ SO ₄ .	Colour on wool.	Colour on cotton.	Absorption maxima.
3-Indole-2'-T (Thioindigo Scarlet R)	...	...	...	4892 Å
3-Indole-2'-(4'-Me)-T	Blue	Dark red	Dark red	4885
3-Indole-2'-(5'-Me)-T	Olive brown	Brilliant scarlet red	Light red	4986
3-Indole-2'-(6'-Me)-T	Olive brown	Red	Light red	4880
3-(5-Chloro) indole-2'-(4'-Me)-T	Blue	Dark red	Dark red	...
3-(5-Chloro) indole-2'-(5'-Me)-T	Olive green	Scarlet red	Scarlet red	...
3-(5-Chloro) indole-2'-(6'-Me)-T	Olive green	Red	Red	...
3-(5-Bromo) indole-2'-(4'-Me)-T	Blue	Dark red	Dark red	...
3-(5-Bromo) indole-2'-(5'-Me)-T	Olive green	Scarlet red	Scarlet red	..
3-(5-Bromo) indole-2'-(6'-Me)-T	Olive green	Red	Red	...
3-(5 :7-Dibromo) indole-2'-T (Ciba Red G)	...	...	...	4915
3-(5 :7-Dibromo) indole-2'-(4'-Me)-T	Blue	Dull red	Deep red	4920
3-(5 :7-Dibromo) indole-2'-(5'-Me)-T	Olive green	Deep red	Deep red	4998
3-(5 :7-Dibromo) indole-2'-(6'-Me)-T	Olive brown	Light scar- let red	Scarlet red	4897
3-(5-Bromo-7-nitro) indole-2'-(4'-Me)-T	Blue	Dark red (dull)	Dark red	...
3-(5-Bromo-7-nitro) indole-2'-(5'-Me)-T	Deep green	Dark red	Dark red	...
3-(5-Bromo-7-nitro) indole-2'-(6'-Me)-T	Yellowish green	Red	Dark red	...
3-(5 :7-Dinitro) indole-2'-T	Blue	Dark red	Dark red	4950
3-(5 :7-Dinitro) indole-2'-(4'-Me)-T	Blue	Dark red	Dark red	4945
3-(5 :7-Dinitro) indole-2'-(5'-Me)-T	Deep green	Dark red	Dark red	5070
3-(5 :7-Dinitro) indole-2'-(6'-Me)-T	Olive brown	Blood red	Dark red	4927

TABLE II.

Compounds.	Absorption maxima	
	longer.	shorter.
Thioindigo (<i>cf.</i> Friedlander and Risse, <i>Ber.</i> , 1914, 47, 1922)	5250 Å	5028 Å*
4 :4'-Dimethyl thioindigo	5248	5025
5 :5'-Dimethyl-thioindigo	5615	5296
6 :6'-Dimethyl-thioindigo	5295	4936

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

4 : 4'-Dimethylthioindigo^s was prepared by the oxidation in the usual way of a pure specimen of 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene. It is soluble in pyridine, aniline, xylene, nitrobenzene and chloroform; moderately soluble in amyl alcohol and acetic acid; sparingly soluble in alcohol and acetone. The solution in concentrated sulphuric acid is green from which water precipitates the original substance. It crystallises from xylene or nitrobenzene in deep red long rectangles. It melts and volatilises when strongly heated above 305°.

3-Indole-2'-(4'-Methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo.

It separated from isatin (0.588 g.) and 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.656 g.) in 85 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 4 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid in silky dark red big needles. The dye (0.898 g.) was crystallised from acetic acid in fine needles. It is moderately soluble in alcohol, difficultly soluble in acetone. It dyes wool in dark red shades from an acid bath and cotton in the same shade from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat. (Found : S, 10.7. C₁₇H₁₁O₂N S requires S, 10.92 per cent).

3-(5-Chloro) indole-2'-(4-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo was obtained as dark red crystalline precipitate by reacting 5-chloroisatin (0.5445 g.) and 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.492 g.) in 80 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 6 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The product (0.75 g.) was crystallised from nitrobenzene in fine dark red clusters of needles. It dyes wool in dark red shades from an acid bath and cotton in nearly the same shade from hydrosulphite vat. (Found : Cl, 11.10. C₁₇H₁₀O₂NClS requires Cl, 10.83 per cent).

3-(5-Bromo)-indole-2'-(4'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo was prepared from 5-bromo-isatin (0.463 g.) and methylhydroxythionaphthene (0.336 g.) in 85 c.c. of acetic acid and 5 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The deep red crystalline substance (0.543 g.) was crystallised in the same way as the preceding compound and it possesses similar properties. (Found : Br, 21.8. C₁₇H₁₀O₂NBrS requires Br, 21.51 per cent).

3-(5:7-Dibromo)-indole-2'-(4'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo separated in the same shape as the corresponding 5'-and 6'-methyl compounds from 5:7-dibromoisatin (0.61 g.) and 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) in 80 c.c. of acetic acid and 5 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The dye (0.792 g.) crystallised from nitrobenzene in bundles of foliated needles. It dyes wool in dull red shades and cotton in deep red shades. (Found: Br, 35.78. $C_{17}H_9O_2NBr_2S$ requires Br, 35.47 per cent).

3-(5-Bromo-7-nitro)-indole-2'-(4'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo was obtained in dark red crystalline precipitate from 5-bromo-7-nitroisatin (0.542 g.) and 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) in 50 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The substance (0.738 g.) was crystallised from pyridine in fine small needles. It dyes wool and cotton in dark red shades. (Found: Br, 18.23. $C_{17}H_9O_4N_2BrS$ requires Br, 19.18 per cent).

3-(5:7-Dinitro)-indole-2'-(4'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo separated as silky deep scarlet red crystalline precipitate from 5:7-dinitroisatin (0.374 g.) and 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.258 g.) in 40 c.c. of acetic acid and 4 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The condensation product (0.57 g.) was crystallised from nitrobenzene in clusters of long rectangles. It is sparingly soluble in xylene and acetic acid. It dyes wool and cotton in dark red shades. (Found: S, 8.01. $C_{17}H_9O_6N_2S$ requires S, 8.35 per cent).

3-(5:7-Dinitro)-indole-2'-thionaphtheneindigo was prepared by heating 5:7-dinitroisatin (0.711 g.) and 3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.45 g.) in 70 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 4 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 20 minutes. The dark red fine small needles (0.25 g.) was collected and crystallised from nitrobenzene. It does not melt below 305°. The dye is soluble in pyridine, aniline, nitrobenzene; sparingly soluble in xylene, benzene, amyl alcohol, acetone, chloroform and alcohol. The solution in concentrated sulphuric acid is blue. It dyes wool in dark red shades from an acid bath and cotton in the same shade from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat. (Found: S, 8.52. $C_{16}H_7O_6N_2S$ requires S, 8.67 per cent).

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